

The Effect of Typhoon Urduja to the Tourism Development of the Municipality of Naval

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Abstract:- The study aims to determine the effect of typhoon Urduja in the Municipality of Naval based profile, damages, and factors to slow tourism development. The study was conducted to identify the situations of the Municipality of Naval after the typhoon. The study applied the descriptive-survey research design, which is appropriate and relevant to the study's objectives, which shows the actual portrayal of the characteristics of a particular situation. The main subject of this study involved was the employees of the room's accommodation facilities and restaurants as they know the effect of the typhoon to their business. The study applied the descriptive survey research design. The constructed questionnaire that was used as a main data gathering tool in collecting data. The researchers used statistical method of percentage average weighted mean. As a result, factors that cause the slow development of tourism in the Municipality of Naval are the damaged water system, high occupancy rate, and irresponsible garbage waste disposal. The recommendations offered based on findings that hotel and restaurants must make a marketing strategy in times of typhoons to maintain the income, the municipality must know the specific areas that can easily be damaged, pricing method and checking roads and bridges to maintain the supply chain system.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ *Background of the Study:-*

Tourism is the activities of people traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for leisure, business or other purposes for not more than one consecutive year. It is a dynamic and competitive industry that requires the ability to adapt constantly to customer's changing needs and desires, as the customer's satisfaction, safety and enjoyment are particularly the focus of tourism business. It is now recognized as being an economic activity of global significance. As the importance of the activity has increased, so too has the attention given to it by governments, organizations in both the public and private sectors, and academics. It is an introduction to a complex and multi-faceted industry (*Jenkins, 2010*).

A tourism is a collection of activities, services and industries which deliver a travel experience comprising transportation, accommodation, eating and drinking establishments, retail shops, entertainment business and other hospitality services provided for individuals or groups

traveling away from home. The sum of the phenomena and relationships arising the interaction of tourist, business suppliers, host government's and host communities in the process of attracting and hosting these tourists and other visitors (*Macintosh 2006*).

Tourism is a social, cultural and economic phenomenon which entails the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business or professional purposes. These people are called visitors which may be either tourists or excursionists; residents or non-residents, and they imply tourism expenditure (*United Nations World Tourism Organization, 2008*).

However, while tourism is a significant economic force, this industry can be described as highly sensitive to stressor. As an industry comprised of many subsectors including accommodation, transportation, entertainment and food and beverage, there are many components of tourism that are susceptible to change. Stressors that affect tourism such as typhoons have been occurring throughout history (*Papatheodorou, 2010*).

Biliran, a province in Eastern Visayas region has a very definite rainy season every year. About 19 % of the tropical depressions that enter country hit the province. Tropical Storm Urduja hit the province of Biliran, some of the main transportation roads users as they take the longer access from Leyte to Municipality of Naval by travelling around the Province of Biliran.

The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of typhoon Urduja to the tourism and developed intervention mechanism to boost up the tourism in the Province of Biliran.

➤ *Objectives of the Study:-*

This study aims to determine on the effects of typhoon Urduja in the Municipality of Naval based profile, damages, and factors to slow tourism development.

This study sought to answer the following questions:

- To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - ✓ Age;
 - ✓ Address;

- ✓ Gender; and
- ✓ Years in service

- To determine the effect of typhoon Urduja in hotels and restaurants.
- To find out the factors that cause the slow development of tourism in the Municipality of Naval caused by the typhoon Urduja.
- To proposed an action plan or intervention mechanism that would boost up the tourism development in Municipality of Naval.

➤ *Framework of the Study*

This study utilizes the conceptual framework as it is main foundations. It provides the overall schemes and viewpoint of the research that is being presented.

- *Theoretical Framework:-* The study was anchored with Alternative Tourism Development: A Theoretical Background by Eirini Triarchi and Kostas Karamanis,

2016. This discussed the development of tourism market through the alternative forms of tourism. It is about developing new forms of sustainable tourism that integrate local populations and both natural and human environments of host countries.

- *Conceptual Framework:-* The study generally intended to look into the effect of typhoon Urduja to the tourism development in the Municipality of Naval.

As parameters, the following variables were measured: demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, address, gender and years in service; effect of typhoon Urduja in hotels and restaurants; factors that cause the slow development of tourism in the Municipality of Naval caused by typhoon Urduja.

As an output of the study, proposed an action plan or intervention mechanism that would boost up the tourism Development in the Municipality of Naval.

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework of the Study

➤ *Significance of the Study*

The researcher intended to enhance and upgrade the result of the study would provide benefits to the following:

- **LGU (Local Government Unit):-** This study will help them to prepare and to avoid as possible the problems that arise after the typhoon.
- **Teachers:-** The result of the study will provide additional knowledge and information about the recent issues that can be essential to the course subject **which tackles about tourism development changes and factors that affect** tourism industry.
- **Students:-** It can open their mind on the possibilities of how the natural phenomenon affect almost every aspect of the tourism economy.
- **School Administration:-** This can be useful reference for the university to have a deeper understanding about the effects of the typhoon in the Municipality of Naval.
- **Future Researchers:-** The result of the study will provide the researchers of information about the respondents and how to be better and able to conceptualize the needed information and solution to the study.

➤ *Scope and Delimitation*

The study focuses on the effects of typhoon Urduja in Biliran specifically in Municipality of Naval its damages, and factors that slows down the tourism development.

➤ *Definition of Terms*

For further understanding of the terms and concepts used in the study, the following terms are defined conceptually and operationally.

- **Attraction site:-** A tourist destination.
- **Biliran Province:-** Is an island province in the Philippines located in Eastern Visayas region (Region VIII). Biliran is one of the countries smallest and newest province. Formerly a sub-province of Leyte, it became an independent province in year 1992.
- **Tourism:-** Travel to benefit from particular services or activities that are unavailable at home.
- **Tourist:-** A traveler who visits places from home for pleasure.
- **Tourism Industry:-** The service industries which benefits from tourism include transportation services, such as airlines, cruise ships, and taxicabs; hospitality services, such as accommodations, including hotels and resorts; and entertainment venues, such as amusement park, casinos, shopping malls, music venues, and theaters.
- **Typhoon:-** Tropical or a violent storm.
- **Tourism Development:-** The act or process of growing the business of providing hotels, restaurants, entertainment for people who are traveling.

II. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodology of the study. It gives light to the research design, research locale, research subject, research instrument and data gathering procedure used in the interpretation of the findings of the study.

➤ *Research Design*

The study applied the descriptive research design. The design was appropriate and relevant on the objectives of the study which shows the actual portrayal of the characteristics of a particular situation, attempt to understand the reasons behind a certain and how they are acted upon.

➤ *Research Locale*

This study conducted in the Municipality of Naval, Biliran.

➤ *Research Subject*

The main subject of this study involved on the effect of typhoon to their business.

➤ *Research Instruments*

A constructed questionnaire that was used as a main data gathering tool in collecting data was made to suit the objectives of the current study. The research instrument contains into three parts and has a demographic profile in each questionnaire. Part I is for the hotels an restaurants respondents in which they are given ten sets of questions that made to satisfy the objectives of achieving the effect of the typhoon Urduja in the business of the two establishment. Part II is an assessment of the damages cause by the typhoon Urduja in the Municipality of Naval. Part III was made to gather data on how the typhoon affects the community and how they cope up from the catastrophe.

➤ *Data Gathering Procedure*

To produce the needed data, permission and approval is secured from the dean of the College of Tourism to conduct the research, questionnaires are personally administered to the respondents to get the data needed and conduct in-depth interview at the same time. Likewise, retrieval, the data are tabulated and statistically analyzed.

➤ *Data Scoring*

The data collected are segregated, tabulated and scored as follows:

Table 1 Data Collected are Segregated, Tabulated and Scored

Range	Weight	Adjectival Rating
4	3.4 – 4.0	Intense
3	2.6 – 3.3	Moderate
2	1.8 – 2.5	Mild
1	1.0 – 1.7	None

➤ *Data Processing and Analysis*

The researchers analyzed its data by manually counting and grouping the answers in their range and then multiplying it by their equivalent rang, lastly to get the percentage, add all the product and divide it by the number of range which is (4). After that we used a statistical method of percentage and average weighted mean.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter were provided to demonstrate the results, findings and discussions which gathered from the employees

of hotel and restaurants, and residents of barangay in Municipality of Naval based from the objectives of the study showing data with the corresponding analysis, discussions, and implications of the results of the data.

➤ *Profile of the Respondents*

The tables shown are the profile of respondents in term of Age, Gender, and year in Service.

- Table 2 below presents the Age, Gender and Years of service of the respondents.

Table 2 Age of the Respondents

Age	F	%
Adult (51 years old)	1	10.00
Young Adult (31-50 years old)	5	50.00
Young (15-30)	4	40.00
TOTAL	10	100.00
Gender	F	%
Male	3	33.33
Female	7	66.67
TOTAL	10	100.00
Years in Service	F	%
Below 1 year	5	50.00
1-5 years	2	20.00
6-9 years	1	10.00
10 years above	2	20.00
TOTAL	10	100.00

The table shows that 40% of the respondents are young adults, while young and adults has 50% respondents in the survey while 66.67 percent of the respondents are female, while male respondents only has one third of the overall percentage or 33.33%. In years of service, it shows that 50% of the respondents are still 1 year in service and 20% are in the range of 1-5 years in service.

➤ *Effect of the Typhoon Urduja on Hotels and Restaurants in the Municipality of Naval*

In table 3 it shows the effects of the typhoon on hotels and restaurants in the Municipality of Naval.

Table 3 Effect of the Typhoon Urduja on Hotels and Restaurants in the Municipality of Naval

Effect of the Typhoon on Hotels and Restaurants in Naval	Hotels		Restaurants	
	W.M.	Description	W.M.	Description
1. Does the number of visitors decrease after the typhoon Urduja?	1	None	1.2	None
2. Does the supply delayed to deliver	1	None	1.6	None
3. Is there a facility that has been damaged?	3.4	Intense	3.2	Moderate
4. Does your income decrease after the Typhoon Urduja?	3	Moderate	2.6	Moderate
5. Do you feel uncomfortable in staying in your workplace?	1.8	Mild	1	None
6. Does your establishment stop cater events just like before after the typhoon Urduja?	0	N/A	1.8	Mild
7. Did you encounter problems in your establishments after the typhoon Urduja?	3.2	Moderate	3.2	Moderate
8. Does your service fee increase after typhoon Urduja?	2.2	Mild	3	Moderate
AVERAGE	2.2	Mild	2.2	Mild

Table 3 displays that the total average weighted mean on the effects of typhoon Urduja to hotels is 2.0 in which the effect is mild, while the average weighted mean on the effects of the typhoon Urduja to restaurant is 2.2 it means the effect is mild. This implies that the typhoon hs only a mild effect on both establishments and still they can entertain the need of the visitors and tourist In the Municipality of Naval.

➤ *Factors that Causes the slow development of tourism in Municipality of Naval caused by the typhoon Urduja*
 Table 4 shows the cause of slow development of tourism caused by the typhoon Urduja.

Table 4 Factors that cause the slow development of tourism in Municipality of Naval caused by the typhoon Urduja

Factors	W.M.	Description
1. Delayed rehabilitation of the damaged tourist spots.	3	Agree
2. Damaged water system	4	Strongly Agree
3. Remaining debris of the trees due to typhoon.	3	Agree
4. Unapproachable people cause tourist to decide not to be back.	2	Disagree
5. Insufficient fund for the tourism development	3	Agree
6. High occupancy rate of hotels.	4	Strongly Agree
7. Irresponsible people in throwing garbage cause polluted surroundings.	4	Strongly Agree
8. Means of access to enter the Municipality of Naval as the main roads are damaged.	4	Strongly Agree
9. Quality of service to the tourist	2	Disagree
10. Culture and local traditions.	2	Disagree

Table 4 shows that the damage of water system, high occupancy of hotels, irresponsible people throwing garbage anywhere causes polluted surroundings and means of access to enter the municipality of Naval as the main roads are damaged are the greatest factor of the slow tourism development in the municipality of Naval. While the unapproachable people cause tourist to decide not to be back, quality of service to the tourist and culture and local traditions are not much effect to the slow effect of tourism.

service to the tourist and culture and local traditions are not much effect to the slow of effect of tourism.

❖ *Conclusion*

- In consonance with the result of the findings the following conclusion were made.
- It is concluded that the female staff is dominant than the male staff in hotel and restaurants.
- The moment news spread that the main roads going to municipality of Naval is not passable. Tourist travel around the province, passing the six municipalities of Biliran if they want to go to Naval – Leyte or Leyte – Naval.
- Low number of tourist is due to massive destruction of typhoon Urduja they are scared of the danger.
- They easily cope the extreme damage of the damaged caused by the typhoon Urduja to the hotel and restaurants resulted the effect of typhoon just to be mild.

❖ *Recommendation*

The following recommendations are offered based on the findings and conclusion of the study.

- Hotels and restaurants must make a marketing strategy in times of typhoons to maintain their income. These establishments must be prepared in terms of supply shortage after the typhoon to provide quality service even after the typhoon.
- The municipality must be alert in all times and must know the certain area that can easily be damage in terms of typhoon, also they must launch a project to protect and preserve the natural tourist spots in their municipality in order to easily renovate it after the typhoon.
- The municipality must be in prepared and has a stock of basic necessities for residents and also for the visitors. Water is the number one basic need of every living so the municipality must work hard in order to give it all times.

IV. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The following chapter concludes the report. A summary of findings is presented, and findings of the study are discussed. Recommendations are also shown for further research of the chapter.

❖ *Summary of Findings*

The following are the finding of the study:-

- The result of the profile of the respondents is that 10% of the respondents are adults, while young adult has 50% respondents in the survey. While 66.67 % of the respondents are female, while male respondents only has one third of the overall percentage or 33.33%. In years of service, it shows that 50% of the respondents are still 1 year below in service and 20% are in the range of 1-5 years in service.
- The effect of the typhoon Urduja on hotels and restaurants in the municipality of Naval it displays that the hotel average weighted mean on the effects of typhoon Urduja to restaurant is 2.2 it means the effect is mild.
- Factors that cause the slow development of tourism in municipality of Naval caused by the typhoon Urduja are the damage of water system, high occupancy of hotels, irresponsible people throw garbage anywhere causes polluted surroundings and means of access to enter the municipality of Naval as the main roads are damaged are the greatest factor of the slow tourism development in the municipality of Naval. While the unapproachable people cause tourist to decide not to be back, quality of

- The municipality must check the prices in the market to prevent illegal price increasing and maintain the value of the products. They must also check the road and bridges for safety of the visitors and commuters passing by and secure plug control all the times to prevent floods.
- To proposed an action plan or intervention mechanism that would boost up the tourism development in the Municipality of Naval

Table 5 below shows the intervention mechanism that would boost up the tourism development.

Table 5 Proposed an action that would boost up the tourism development

Proposed Activity/ Action taken	Persons Involved
Posting rehabilitated spots in Municipality of Naval to attract tourist	Social Media Influencer
Create a travel itinerary that features the beauty of the municipality	Travel Agencies
Implementing fines to people who do improper garbage disposal	LGU- Naval
Implement monthly youth clean and green drive service in the municipality	Barangay Officials

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